

The Breakup of Pakistan in the context of the Modern History Of Pakistan.(1970-71)

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Abstract:

The research paper “The Breakup of Pakistan in the context of the Modern History Of Pakistan.(1970-71) “ Is selected to find various accesses in completing the topic. After1947 the successive government of Pakistan treated the east wing as atrociously as it was in their power It is a long story, but put in stark, brief words East Bengal was denied everything to which it was entitled as a constituent part of the federation, moral Support, Adequate foreign exchange, majority in the national legislature ,proportionate seats in the cabinet and ministries, just and equitable representation in the federal civil service, proper share in the armed forces, etc. This topic is very controversial and very suspicious. In fact the eastern wing was separated because of various reasons, those are may known as, economically, politically, socially, geographically, culturally, which are called responsible segregating and unstable relationship between these two states. After existence of Pakistan the relationship between Eastern wing and Western wing has been rendered tumultuous and since creation of newly state due to misunderstanding between two wings, many problems were created and it was changed under serious unprecedented situation which was observed on 16 December 1971.
Keywords: - Pakistan, East wing, Awami league, sheikh mujeeb, separation.

Introduction

Pakistan was consist of two parts known as east Pakistan and west Pakistan the distance between east Pakistan and west Pakistan was about 1600 km and around 100 miles.

East Pakistan was territory of Bangali people and west Pakistan was majority of the people belonged different languages but used Urdu as a national language.

West Pakistan considered biggest wing on territorial base, on the hand East Pakistan was the biggest wing on bases of population. after independence Pakistan need to frame a new constitution to run the governmental office but the Indian act of 1935 with some amendments was imposed on temporarily bases until a new permanent constitution was to form, the people of east Pakistan who were in majority on population bases faced injustice when constitution framing process begun. The Bengalis demand was that to distribute seats on population bases and impose Bengali as a national language as Bengalis are in majority.

The leader belonging to West Pakistan rejected this demand of East Pakistan the basic principle committee was established to abolish constitutional conflict but the recommendations of basic principle committees were rejected due to distribution of seat on equal bases and on language issue. Bogra formula was presented by Muhammad Ali Bogra, the prime minster. It was a good formula but distribution of seats of in the upper house was on unequal bases which continued the political conflicts and caused the political instability in the country.

One unit scheme was the plane of chaudhary Muhammad Ali to divide the country into two wings, but to unite the four provinces of west Pakistan into one unit to make the constitution framing process easy and the distribution of seats on population bases was considered a good formula but the constitution remained imposed in the country for two years, the martial law of Ayub khan who belonged to west Pakistan become the president with absolute power and abolished parliamentary form of government, dissolved the constituent assembly ,abrogated the first constitution of Pakistan. The distribution of seats of national assembly in the regime of

Ayub Khan was on equal bases consisting of 150 seats 75 seats to East Pakistan and 75 seats to West Pakistan which was injustice due to over population and extreme problem.

In 1966 Sheikh Mujeeb presented his six points to federal Government and those were not accepted by the president Ayub Khan and western Pakistan.

In 1970 before the election the flood affects and sonami effects increased anger in Bengalis where a large number of people had to loss their lives but the Bengalis were not helped at the right time.

The Indian interference through a Russian treaty after the 1965 were defeating paused the way for Bangalies for separation.

The Causes for separation of eastern wing.

Division of Muslim league

Muslim league was the sole political organization which played a vital role in establishment of Pakistan on 11 September 1948 Quaid e Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah died after his death there was not such a leader who could run the Muslim league organization the gape which was left by Quaid e Azam nobody fulfilled it and there was same internal problem in Muslim league political party. Due to those problems Muslim organization was broken and divided in different groups. After the Muslim league division few political parties came into being democratic people party, Jinha Awami league, and National Awami party were political parties which came into being after division of Muslim league.

Molvi Fazal ul haque was that chairman of Awami league in 1954 provincial election were held in East Pakistan Awami league successes election. Few years later Sheikh Mujeeb elected as the chairman of Awami league. At the leading of Sheikh Mujeeb Awami league begun first politics, especially in east Pakistan Awami league took part in general election of 1970 and successes in east Pakistan with huge margin. This political party got the public mandate in provincial and national assembly.

Muslim league became weak after division, so the Awami league asked to guide people in every plate from eastern Pakistanis, this party opposed the martial law and started to criticize West Pakistan.

Awami league protested and demanded different aspects and this party which came from Muslim league was the main political party which played partial role against western Pakistan and especially for separation and the division of Muslim league was a main cause of separation.

[01]

Distance between two wings

The basic reason which erected many difficulties and more causes toward separation was the distance between both wings of Pakistan it was a big issue. Geographically East Pakistan situated on the eastern border of India and Indian territory was between the both wings of Pakistan. There was a long gape and this gape was around 100 miles. The distance erected many problems in communication and in other field as well, so it was the basic reason which provides chance to the enemy and neighboring country, which created problems for these both wings of Pakistan. The distance was not only a geographically a problem in other field of country as like administration. Safety of border from all around neighboring countries socially and economically problems were being faced due to distance in every field of country. As it was huge problem because when Sir Red Cliff divided both countries it was not at the fever of Pakistan impact it was divided with chosen areas of Hindus [2] as it was not been thought about the both the both wings which a long distance will create many problems for the people of both wings. So it was also created see unity threats after the India Pakistan war of 1965 because it

was difficult for the army at the time of war to protect both wings of Pakistan. It means distance was basic roots towards separation due to erecting money socially, economically problems for government of Pakistan. [3]

Language issue.

Language is the identification of a nation which shows the existence of a nation. After freedom big clash happened between the eastern Pakistan and western Pakistan. This clash was for national league of country. When the its constitutional assembly meeting held. A pollination from eastern Pakistan amended that “the member of assembly eastern Pakistan would be permitted to express or use Bengal language in assembly for the speech” but the prime minister of Pakistan Liaquat Ali Khan denied and ordered with hard words “that Urdu is the only language which brought the people of both wings together” due to this replied of prime minister eastern Pakistan were dishearted. Another reason those affairs who belonged from West Pakistan could do their works in English and Urdu. Spite of this those affairs were not ready to learn Bengali issue. The Urdu language was become a serious issue the Urdu language was selected as national language in objective revolution. But same facts which were maintained above brought Bengalis for protest at the fever of Bengali language. The Bengalis demanded “the population of eastern Pakistan is in majority then western Pakistan “so Bengali should be use as national language of Pakistan like Urdu but in western Pakistan many nations were living and the all were at same pitch, spite of it all western Pakistan supported the Urdu language as national language. After the protests of eastern Pakistanis and for their wishes in 1953 Bengali language was selected as national language in Bogra’s formula at least eastern Pakistanis successes to make Bengali as national language in first constitution of Pakistan there were two national languages “Urdu” and “Bengali”. Both languages were selected as national language. It was continued up to the separation. Both over all it brought few gapes between control government and eastern Pakistan and it also pumped the eastern Pakistanis for the future. [4]

The Martial law of Ayub Khan up to Yahya’s Martial Law

On 27 October 1958 Ayub Khan became the president of Pakistan with absolute power. He was the chief of the Army staff and administrator of martial law. He took changed as second president of Pakistan president Ayub Khan abolished the parliamentary form of government with his absolute power. And also abolished the set of prime minister which increased in the deprivation of eastern Pakistanis. So after the Ayub’s Martial Law eastern Pakistanis were disproved from the seat of prime minister which was hearted then and it was also unfair with them. Other side they brought party, which was also injustice with them. So the same president form of government continued up to Yahya’s Martial Law which was imposed for second time and Yahya became the third president of Pakistan and more than two years period. The presidential form of government also dishearted the eastern Pakistanis and it can be said a huge of separation. [5]

Parity between both wings

In Bogra formula the western Pakistan became a unit it was consisted on four provinces . After Bogra formula in the 1st constitution of Pakistan 1956 there were two parts of Pakistan, one East Pakistan and second West Pakistan. The East Pakistan was a majority on the bases of population then West Pakistan. In first constitution they brought parity and did not provide seats in constitution assembly according to the population.

First constitution 1956:-

In first there were three hundred seats of assembly. 165 seats were given to East Pakistan and 135 seats were for West Pakistan. It was injustice because east Pakistanis were in majority on population bases but they had given less seats and less members of according to their population. The eastern Pakistan was opposed the parity.

Second constitution 1962:-

Same things happened in second constitution of 1962 of Pakistan. Here again the numbers of seats were less. There Was 150 seats over 6 seats for women. But those seats divided equally to the both wings on parity 75 seats for East Pakistan and 75 seats for West Pakistan 3 women seats for East Pakistan and 3 women seats for West Pakistan. [6]

Six points of Sheikh Mujeeb

In February 1966 after the war of 1965 between Pakistan and India Sheikh Mujeeb presented six points. Which are noted below?

1. Federal, parliamentary system representation on basis of population and principal of party was rejected.
2. Federal government to deal with only two subjects.
 - I. Defense
 - II. Foreign policy affairs

All residuary power was to be vested in the provinces.

3. Provision of two separate currencies easily countable if there was only one currency then effective constitutional provision to stop the flight of capital from East Pakistan to West Pakistan.
4. The power of taxation and revenue collection to be vested to the federating unit the federation will have share from the federation units.
5. Provision for two separate accounts for foreign exchanges the federating units shall meet foreign exchange requirement of federal government.
6. The setting up Militia and port Military force for East Pakistan.

These six points were not accepted by government and after election and political conflict Sheikh Mujeeb insisted again revised his six points. Before the election with six points he brought changes in mind set of people and his arresting, these six points proved him as a hero, but still these demands were not accepted. But at least those six points changed the game and by India support separated east part from west part Pakistan. [7]

Flood and sunami before the election 1970.

Before the general election of 1970 almighty Allah brought situational exam for the government and management as well which was big challenge for them naturally it rained deeply this rain was continued for few days. After deeply rain flood water came in eastern Pakistan in the month of September. It destroyed a long area of East Pakistan. All the managements were damaged. Thousands of people lost their houses, thousands of families were sundered from their family members. It also effected communication system badly people were worried and there were no any help for them at the time of a huge exam but in front of almighty Allah nobody could not do anything so people beard huge and blander damages of flood water.

These hurts which were given and left by flood water were not fulfilled that almighty Allah brought the eastern Pakistanis In a new hard exam. It was sunami which came in 12 September 1970, it damaged more areas of Pakistan it destroyed a large number of people around 5 lakes. They lost their lives. It was hurtful. In this hurtful situation people lost their properties and it was tragic.

On the first day of sunami Army reached all those affected areas which were damaged and very far. The army begun to support the effected people and helped them by helicopter.

It is right these support and help were not enough in a large number of populations but it is also wrong to blame same one for year benefit.

Awami league criticized against West Pakistan and government as blamed for external funding that was not given them. The Awami league was united to prove it as it the only party which can fight for rights. So people were affected from awami league they also supported, but infect it was conspires of India as they used the naturally situation as tool against West Pakistan. [8]

Election of 1970 and Success of Awami league in eastern Pakistan and political instability.

After Martial law of Ayub khan in December 1970. The general election was started and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto successes in western Pakistan Awami league Sheikh Mujeeb Successive in East Pakistan. There were 313 seats totally sheikh mujeeb achieved 167 seats over all but Zulfiqar Ali got only 88 seats in this way Awamu league become the majority and in western Pakistani people's party the majority party. After successes in election sheikh MUjeeb Announced that we got success and we are in majority we will form government without participation of western party. But the western party ppp opposed the Awami league Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto said without our participation the eastern party cannot establish government. Bhutto said" neither we go there nor they come here" and at same when he announced that "Dhaka is a letter said by Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto but sheikh Mujeeb also replied the same word to Islamabad. So the political conflict started between eastern Pakistan and western Pakistan. This political instability caused separation.[9]

Non-cooperation movement

Sheikh Mujeeb was started a movement for a week on March 1971. It was strong movement. Sheikh Mujeeb announced the purpose of this movement will be continuing till achieving our purpose it will continue till the demands are not accepted.

"The main purpose of this movement was to abolish martial law immediately and power should be hand over to elected members".

This movement was started against Yahiya khan in noncooperation movement sheikh Mujeeb boycotted and called Bengalis for disobedience which was given under.

1. Do not pay taxes.
2. Strikes in all government institutes, high courts.
3. Railway stations and reports would be continue but the labor and other people who are working they would not help the Pakistani army against the Bengalis
4. Radio and T.V will telecast all news and newspaper will publish that news as well news would not publish and telecast so those Bengali workers who are working in these institutes will not help them.
5. Educational institutes will be off.
6. Political flag will rise in all institutes every day.
7. Bank does not transfer money to western Pakistan by state bank or other sources.

This non-cooperation movement pressured and bank was closed and did not serve its account holders. Bank also followed that which was the purpose of Awami league.

T.V and radio broad casting and newspaper were publishing that news which was given them by the Awami league workers.

This cooperation also pressured on Yahiya's government. At least this non-cooperation helped Awami league towards separation. [10]

Request for Agitation

The political party Awami league of East Pakistan was successive in election of 1970. Awami league was leading the East Pakistan in March 1971 the workers of awami league started blood agitation in Dhaka city. All government officers, courts, educational institutes were off due to blood agitation in the half month of March there was cruelty everywhere in Dhaka. The western Pakistanis were preset in Dhaka they went for visit but situation changed suddenly. The workers of Awami league were against of western Pakistanis they begun to kill people in different areas of Dhaka.

Bogra District:-

The Awami league's workers killed fifteen thousand people in bogra district. Which were belonging to West Pakistan.

Chittagong:-

As this agitation started same situation were in chittgong as well as. They deprived in thousands people from their lives and there were seven hundred woman and children from them who were killed by eastern Pakistanis as well.

Siraj Nagar:-

It was triage incidence which happened in siraj nagger three hundred woman and Childs were burnt alive they were imprisoned by Awami league's workers in a hall.

This agitation created more gapes between both wings and it also push the situation separation due to Bengalis .[11]

Bureaucracy

After the establishment of Pakistan bureaucracy was started its monopoly in different governmental institutes, especially in defence, courts, secteriet. They were using the political parties and pollinations on his own wishes, the pollination were under control of bureaucracy and inn different institutes western Pakistanis were captured job. As it was right snatching force eastern Pakistanis were thinking it was injustice with them. They were opposed the monopoly which was being happening from western Pakistanis. They started protest their basic right and seats which were under control of bureaucracy eastern Pakistanis reaction against bureaucracy.

Due to monopoly of bureaucracy the eastern Pakistanis raised voice against of bureaucracy. They were fed up from monopoly and it was also a cause of sundrenched. [12]

Developmental Programs

Another cause which effected the eastern Pakistanis foe separation and for demand as well as, was the development program which government come and took power they made different development programs for country as well as for both wings. But power were given to western Pakistan as after the minister was abolished that according to the constitution of 1956 prime minister should be selected from the eastern Pakistan as present is from western Pakistan. So they had no power, in development programs eat Pakistan was ignored the West Pakistan. Because those development programs which begun were not enough according to the population of east Pakistan, many factories and industries were planted in eastern Pakistan but those were not well enough according to population majority and west Pakistan was also ignored in the field of education and health seats as well, the need of schools, colleges and hospitals were in more number, people were not facilitated, the poverty and unemployment increasing day by day. Eastern Pakistanis were back ward in economy perfection.

Comparing East Pakistan to West Pakistan according to the population the number of unemployed people was in majority then the West Pakistan. They were thinking about their rights which were not given them they demanded different things from West Pakistan. It was also a fact which brought eastern Pakistanis for demanding separation.

Example:-

In 1952 the (PIDC) Pakistan industries development cooperation was established for the purpose of new plant industries about different purpose, and it was given to years task till 1962, and It planted 55 industries in both wings of Pakistan but in 1962 it was decided that the PIDC should be in two parts in both wings after two parts of PDIC 33 industries become the part of west Pakistan and only 22 industries remains in eastern wing which was injustice with Bangalies according to the population. [13]

Interference of Hindus in Eastern Pakistan

Geographically Indian Territory was between the both wings of Pakistan, the border of East Pakistan and west both were connected with Indian border and after the land distribution of subcontinent Bengalis around they will remain with Pakistan and Bengal was remind in Pakistan. In Bengal Muslims were in majority in population and non muslims were in minority some Hindus families remained in Bengal and their relatives were living in India. In East Pakistan those hinder N families were living comfortable life in Bengal.

So those Hindu used to go to India and come to east Pakistan those families were used by India government as espionages against Pakistan they worked as agent for India their relatives were also doing the same thing wherever they went for visit or tour but these were pretense of them.

Many Hindus were school teacher they were also involved in sponging for India. The Hindu teachers guided the students against Pakistan and trained by those teachers as well.

Due to wrong guidance students begun negative against West Pakistan and thinned West Pakistan as their enemy. Teachers changed the mindset of students hated from Pakistan. As like India want to subdue Pakistan so India used the Hindus teacher for subdue of Pakistan.

So that's why the iterance of India by secret way of supporting to western Pakistanis bought them against West Pakistan and they demand for separation.

Interference of neighboring country (India)

The eastern Pakistan was located at important area. India did not know the value of East Pakistan's territory before of 1965 between Pakistan and india. India started interference from war 1962 which was against china. At that India requested to president of Pakistan Ayub khan to permit the India for using the territory of East Pakistan against chin, but Ayub khan ignored it. India could not help his Army which was in "Assam" and from those days India interference was in erased day by day.

War of 1965:-

In this war Pakistan defeated India badly. After this war India took more interest to revenge from Pakistan.

Importance of Bengal:-

Bengal was located at important area. India felt importance of it after the war of 1965. And India from the first day was against of Pakistan for capturing upon Bengal India in erased interference.

High jack of Ganga Airline:-

The Kashmiri mujahedeen high jacked the India Ganga airline. It was going from rising to Dhaka. Two Kashmiri mujahedeen high jacked it and landed at airport of Lahore. There were 26 passengers and 4 staff in airline. After landing in Lahore airport on 30 March 1971, those passengers were safely brought out from airplane and took to the hotel, on 31 March 1971 Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto met with mujahedeen, asked them the reason this action. The Mujahedeen replied that “they are fighting against India back India occupied on Kashmir and demanded if India would not leave their other colleges who were in prison they will destroy the prison, but Indian government ignored this demand of mujahedeen and Kashmiri mujahedeen destroyed the prison the airplane, but blamed Pakistan and called Pakistan responsible for it. So these all the reasons which India interfered in eastern Pakistan. India not only used the eastern Hindus as against but also support in different platform Bengal, as India was a backbone for Bengal against West Pakistan. India supported the Bengalis against the Pakistani army.

India offered for military help to Sheikh Mujeeb after 1971 war.

India offered for weapons.

Sheikh Mujeeb was fully supported by India.

India left 25 lacs western Pakistanis in the duration of war of 1971 in India.

In Shimla India also demanded for separation of Bengal, because India promised with for occupation of Bengal seaport.

So India interfered different time in different way at least East Pakistan separated from West Pakistan. [14]

Conclusion

Eastern Pakistan was not separated on wishes of western Pakistanis and neither was it a plan but it happened on the wishes of them. As on above paragraphs mention the interference of India. Over all from the starting we saw few weakness of governments and from western Pakistan as well, but the eastern Pakistanis were followed the treks and conspiracies of India. They killed innocent people, the begun non-cooperation movement ignored the western political party as participation in establishment of government and they also blamed and the naturally situation used as tool against Pakistan but overall it was totally happened due to interference of India. If India would not interfered in internal problems of Pakistan so may east Pakistan is still a part of west Pakistan. In fact the eastern wing was separated because of various reasons, those are may know as, economically, politically, socially, geographically, culturally, which are called responsible segregating and unstable relationship between these two states. After existence of Pakistan the relationship between Eastern wing and Western wing has been rendered tumultuous and since creation of newly state due to misunderstanding between two wings, many problems were created and it was changed under serious unprecedented situation which was observed on 16 December 1971.

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